

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

2025, №6 (20)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

Научный журнал по фундаментальным и клиническим
проблемам медицины
основан в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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2025, № 6 (20)

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*Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28 мая 2022 года.*

*Журнал внесен в список
утвержденный приказом № 370/6
от 8 мая 2025 года реестром ВАК
в раздел медицинских наук.*

Отпечатано в типографии ООО
“Шарк-Бухоро”. г. Бухара,
ул. Ўзбекистон Мустақиллиги, 70/2.

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THE ROLE OF LAPAROSCOPIC SURGERY IN THE RECURRENCE OF CERVICAL CANCER**Mamedov U.S., Nurov J.R., Abdurahimova Y.A.**

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Resume. *Objective of the Study: Based on multifactorial analysis, to evaluate the effectiveness, safety, and long-term outcomes (one-year mortality, overall survival, recurrence rate, localization, and time of recurrence) of minimally invasive and open radical hysterectomy in early-stage cervical cancer (CC). Materials and Methods: The study was conducted from 2010 to 2023 in the Oncology Gynecology Department of the Bukhara branch of RIO and RIATM. Inclusion criteria: (1) histologically confirmed cervical cancer, including all histological types; (2) stages IA1 - IIA2 (FIGO 2018); (3) extended hysterectomy (Type III) with pelvic and/or para-aortic lymphadenectomy as the primary surgical treatment. Patients with insufficient data were excluded. Depending on the surgical access, patients were divided into two groups: minimally invasive surgery and open surgery. Results: The analysis was conducted based on the following parameters: age, stage (FIGO 2018), substage by TNM, tumor histotype, tumor size, obstetric-gynecological history, comorbidities, primary treatment method, surgical access, tumor size, duration of surgery, blood loss volume, need for subsequent adjuvant therapy, intra- and postoperative complications. Additionally, long-term results were assessed in each group: overall survival and recurrence-free survival, one-year mortality. Conclusion: The results obtained in both groups were comparable, including overall and recurrence-free survival, indicating the safety and effectiveness of minimally invasive surgery compared to open surgery.*

Keywords: *cervical cancer, laparoscopic surgery, recurrences, overall survival, open hysterectomy.*

РОЛЬ ЛАПАРОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ ХИРУРГИИ В РЕЦИДИВАХ РАКА ШЕЙКИ МАТКИ**Мамедов У.С., Нуров Дж.Р., Абдурахимова Ё.А.**

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Резюме. *Цель исследования: На основе многократного анализа оценить эффективность, безопасность и долгосрочные результаты (одногодичная летальность, общая выживаемость, частота рецидивов, локализация и время рецидива) минимально инвазивной и открытой радикальной гистерэктомии при ранних стадиях рака шейки матки (РШМ). Материалы и методы: Исследование было проведено в период с 2010 по 2023 годы в отделении онкогинекологии Бухарского филиала РИО и РИАТМ. Критерии включения: (1) гистологически подтвержденный рак шейки матки, включая все гистологические типы; (2) стадии IA1 - IIA2 (FIGO 2018); (3) расширенная гистерэктомия (Тип III) с тазовой и/или парааортальной лимфаденэктомией как основной метод хирургического лечения. Пациенты с недостаточными данными были исключены. В зависимости от хирургического доступа пациенты были разделены на две группы: минимально инвазивная хирургия и открытая хирургия. Результаты: Анализ проводился по следующим параметрам: возраст, стадия (FIGO 2018), подстадия по TNM, гистотип опухоли, размер опухоли, акушерско-гинекологический анамнез, сопутствующие заболевания, первичный метод лечения, хирургический доступ, размер опухоли, продолжительность операции, объем кровопотери, необходимость последующей адъювантной терапии, интраоперационные и послеоперационные осложнения. Также были оценены долгосрочные результаты в каждой группе: общая выживаемость и выживаемость без рецидивов, однодичная летальность. Заключение: Полученные результаты в обеих группах были сопоставимы, включая общую выживаемость и выживаемость без рецидивов, что подтверждает безопасность и эффективность минимально инвазивной хирургии по сравнению с открытой хирургией.*

Ключевые слова: *рак шейки матки, лапароскопическая хирургия, рецидивы, общая выживаемость, открытая гистерэктомия.*

БАЧАДОН БЎЙНИ САРАТОНИ РЕЦИДИВЛАРДА ЛАПАРОСКОПИК ХИРУРГИЯНИНГ РОЛИ**Мамедов У.С., Нуров Ж.Р., Абдурахимова Ё.А.**

Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. *Тадқиқот мақсади: Кўп омилли таҳлил асосида, эрта босқичдаги бачадон бўйни раки (ШМР)да кам инвазив ва очиқ радикал гистерэктомиянинг самарадорлиги, хавфсизлиги ва узоқ муддатли натижалари (бир йиллик леталлик, умумий тирикчилик, рецидивлар даражаси, локализацияси ва рецидив вақти)ни баҳолаш. Материаллар ва усуллар: Тадқиқот 2010-2023 йиллар давомида РИО*

ва РИАТМ Бухоро филиали онкогинекология бўлимида ўтказилган. Кўшиши критерийлари: (1) гистологик тасдиқланган бачадон бўйни раки, барча гистологик турлар; (2) IA1 - IIA2 босқичлари (FIGO 2018); (3) кенгайтирилган гистерэктомия (Тип III) ва тазо ва/ёки парааортал лимфаденэктомия асосий хирургик даволаш усули сифатида. Маълумотлари етишимовчи беморлар *chiqarib* ташланди. Хирургик киришни инобатга олиб, беморлар икки гуруҳга бўлинди: кам инвазив хирургия ва очиқ хирургия. Натижалар: Таҳлил қуйидаги параметрлар бўйича олиб борилди: ёш, босқич (FIGO 2018), TNM бўйича паст босқич, пухтаги гистотип, ўсма ўсиши ҳажми, акушер-гинекологик анамнез, ҳамронлик касалликлари, биринчи даволаш усули, хирургик кириши, пухта ўсиши ҳажми, операция давомийлиги, қон йўқотиши миқдори, кейинги адъювант терапияга эҳтиёж, операция давомида ва кейинги асоратлар. Шунингдек, ҳар бир гуруҳда узоқ муддатли натижалар баҳоланган: умумий тирикчилик ва рецидивсиз тирикчилик, бир йиллик леталлик. Хулоса: Ҳар икки гуруҳда олинган натижалар умумий ва рецидивсиз тирикчилик бўйича таққосланди, бу эса кам инвазив хирургиянинг очиқ хирургияга нисбатан хавфсизлиги ва самарадорлигини кўрсатади.

Калит сўзлар: бачадон бўйни раки, лапароскопик хирургия, рецидивлар, умумий тирикчилик, очиқ гистерэктомия.

Introduction. Cervical cancer (CC) is one of the most common malignant neoplasms worldwide. According to the global GLOBOCAN statistics, the incidence of CC in 2022 was 662,301 cases, and the mortality rate was 348,874 [1]. Surgical treatment is the primary method for early-stage disease [2]. Radical hysterectomy with or without lymphadenectomy (depending on the disease stage) allows for tumor removal and assessment of risk factors, as well as the need for adjuvant therapy. Over the past decade, endoscopic treatment methods have gained wide popularity, including in oncology and gynecology. In 2018, laparoscopic access for the treatment of early-stage cervical cancer was included in the ESGO guidelines [3]. However, the unexpected results of the LACC study were published shortly thereafter. The LACC study is a multicenter, randomized controlled phase III trial aimed at evaluating overall and recurrence-free survival in minimally invasive versus open radical hysterectomy for IA2-IB1 stages of cervical cancer. The results showed worse long-term outcomes for minimally invasive surgery. The three-year recurrence-free survival was 91.2% for minimally invasive surgery and 97.1% for open surgery. Similarly, the three-year overall survival was 93.8% in the minimally invasive group compared to 99% in the open surgery group. These findings sparked a wave of new studies dedicated to surgical approaches in cervical cancer treatment [4]. Subsequently, many studies were conducted that did not identify any worsening of long-term outcomes, although most of these studies were retrospective in nature [5, 6].

From 2020 to 2022, attempts were made to consolidate the accumulated experience in meta-analyses and systematic reviews, which also refuted the claims about the unsafety of minimally invasive surgery for cervical cancer [7, 8, 9].

Thus, there is still no consensus or definitive conclusions regarding the applicability of minimally invasive surgery in cervical cancer treatment. According to the global recommendations of NCCN, ESGO, and ESMO, minimally invasive surgery is recommended only for tumors smaller than 2 cm. Given the relevance of this topic, we have summarized our own long-term experience with extended radical hysterectomy for early-stage cervical cancer [2, 10].

Objective: Based on multifactorial analysis, to evaluate the effectiveness, safety, and long-term outcomes (one-year mortality, overall survival, recurrence rate, localization, and time of recurrence) of minimally invasive and open radical hysterectomy for early-stage cervical cancer.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted from 2010 to 2023 in the Oncology Gynecology Department of the Bukhara branch of RIO and RIATM.

A total of 212 patients with IA1 (LVI+) to IIA2 stages were included. All patients underwent extended radical hysterectomy (type III PIVER) with or without pelvic and/or para-aortic lymphadenectomy. For laparoscopic radical hysterectomy, the Clermont-Ferrand uterine manipulator with a Karl Storz atraumatic inserter was used.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age ≥ 18 years;
2. Histologically confirmed cervical cancer (squamous cell carcinoma, adenocarcinoma);
3. Stages IA1 (with lymphovascular invasion) to IIA2 according to FIGO;
4. Extended radical hysterectomy (type III) with pelvic and/or para-aortic lymphadenectomy as the primary treatment.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with insufficient data were excluded.

Patients were divided into two groups depending on the surgical access method. The design of the study is shown in Figure 1.

The study evaluated age, tumor histotype, presence of lymph node metastases, disease stage, tumor size, primary treatment method, intraoperative and postoperative complications, recurrence rate, one-year mortality, and overall survival.

Statistical Analysis: The data for the study were collected in an electronic table with a long-format structure, followed by an examination for completeness and input errors. Exploratory data analysis was then performed using Tukey's method to detect anomalous values (outliers), the Shapiro-Wilk test for checking normality of continuous data distributions, and the F-test for variance comparison. The results are presented in tables. Examples of graphical analysis of distributions are shown in the figures.

Due to the small number of indicators meeting the applicability conditions for parametric criteria (Student's t-test), the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U-test was used to compare continuous variables between groups at one time point. For evaluating differences (effect size), pseudo-medians of pairwise differences and standardized mean differences with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) were calculated. Descriptive statistics for continuous variables are presented as median [Q1; Q3], and auxiliary statistics as mean \pm standard deviation (mean \pm SD), and range (MIN-MAX). Categorical variables are presented as counts and percentages within each category. Fisher's exact two-sided test was used for comparing categorical variables between groups. The Benjamini-Hochberg method was applied for correcting errors in multiple testing. Binary variables are presented with event counts and percentages (lower and upper bounds of the 95% CI using Wilson's formula). Fisher's exact test was used for comparing binary variables between groups. Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI were calculated to assess the effect size. Correlation coefficients for continuous variables were calculated using Spearman's correlation, and for binary variables with other variables, biserial correlation coefficients were used. Statistical hypothesis testing was performed at a significance level of $p = 0.05$, and differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. Statistical calculations were carried out in RStudio version 2022.07.2+576 (USA) using R language version 4.1.3 (2022-03-10, Austria).

Table 1

Patient Characteristics

Parameter	Open Surgery (n = 147)	Laparoscopic Surgery (n = 65)
Age (years)	42.6 \pm 10.8	44.6 \pm 9.1
Histotype of tumor, n (%)		
Squamous cell carcinoma	117 (79.6 %)	59 (90.8 %)
Adenocarcinoma	30 (20.4 %)	6 (9.2 %)
Metastasis in lymph nodes after surgery, n (%)		
	22 (14.9 %)	1 (1.5 %)
Disease stage, n (%)		
T1a1N0M0 (LV+)	9 (6.1 %)	26 (40 %)
T1a2N0M0	9 (6.1 %)	7 (10.8 %)
T1b1N0M0	69 (46.9 %)	23 (35.4 %)
T1b2N0M0	37 (25.2 %)	4 (6.2 %)
T1b3N0M0	2 (1.4 %)	0
T2a1N0M0	16 (10.9 %)	2 (3.1 %)
T2a2N0M0	3 (2.0 %)	0

Results. Patient Characteristics: The study involved 212 patients, with 147 in the open radical hysterectomy group and 65 in the laparoscopic radical hysterectomy group. The basic characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

The median length of hospitalization was 7 days in the laparoscopic surgery group and 10 days in the open surgery group (Table 2). No significant differences were observed in age or tumor histotype. The rate of intraoperative complications was 3.1% in the laparoscopic surgery group and 2.7% in the open surgery group. The intraoperative complications in the open surgery group included: obturator nerve injury (1 case, 0.68%), external iliac vein injury (1 case, 0.68%), ureter injury (1 case, 0.68%), and bladder injury (1 case,

0.68%). In the laparoscopic surgery group, intraoperative complications included obturator nerve injury (1 case, 1.5%) and ureter injury (1 case, 1.5%).

Postoperative Complications occurred in 6.1% of patients in the open surgery group and 1.5% in the laparoscopic surgery group. In the early postoperative period, bladder atony was observed in 100% of cases, which is not a true complication but a consequence of the extended hysterectomy. Among the early postoperative complications in the open surgery group, the formation of lymphocysts was noted in two patients (1.4%), which required surgical intervention. In one patient (0.68%), a lymphocyst developed an abscess, also requiring surgical treatment. Other postoperative complications included: hematoma of the anterior abdominal wall (2 cases, 1.4%), pelvic abscess (1 case, 0.68%), intra-abdominal hemorrhage (1 case, 0.68%), vaginal stump dehiscence (vaginal necrosis, 1 case, 0.68%), and seroma (separation of aponeurosis edges, 1 case, 0.68%). In the laparoscopic surgery group, vaginal stump dehiscence occurred on the 5-7th postoperative day (1 case, 1.5%). All complications were successfully managed, and the patients were discharged in satisfactory condition. The complications are summarized in Table 3.

Attention should be paid to the complications, as they can delay the initiation of adjuvant radiation therapy. No significant differences were observed between the two groups in terms of the timing of adjuvant therapy. Adjuvant radiation therapy was prescribed in 15.6% of cases in the open surgery group and 6.2% in the laparoscopic surgery group.

Long-term Results. Over the observation period from 2010 to 2023, there were 20 recurrences, representing 9.4% of cases. In the open surgery group, 19 recurrences (12%) occurred, while in the laparoscopic surgery group, there was 1 recurrence (1.5%).

One patient with stage T1a1N0M0 (with lymphovascular invasion) underwent laparoscopic radical hysterectomy with para-aortic lymphadenectomy and ovarian transposition. Histological analysis revealed poorly differentiated squamous cell carcinoma, and no lymph node metastases were detected. A year later, lung metastases were diagnosed, and polychemotherapy (Paclitaxel, Carboplatin) was initiated. Unfortunately, the patient died two years later from disease progression.

In the open surgery group, the time to recurrence ranged from 5 months to 4 years. Seven local recurrences occurred in the vaginal stump, four recurrences with lung metastases, two recurrences in the transposed ovaries, three recurrences in lymph nodes (para-aortic, supraclavicular, inguinal), one patient with liver metastasis, and one with bone metastases. Data on recurrences after open surgery are summarized in Table 4.

The one-year mortality rate was 1.4% in the open surgery group and 0% in the laparoscopic surgery group. The overall survival rates were comparable between the two groups: 95.9% for open surgery and 96.9% for laparoscopic surgery (Table 4).

Table 2

Intraoperative and Postoperative Complications

Complication	Open Surgery (n = 147)	Laparoscopic Surgery (n = 65)
Intraoperative Complications		
Obturator nerve injury	1 (0.68%)	1 (1.5%)
Injury to external iliac vein	1 (0.68%)	0
Ureter injury	1 (0.68%)	1 (1.5%)
Bladder injury	1 (0.68%)	0
Postoperative Complications		
Lymphocyst (required surgical treatment)	2 (1.4%)	0
Lymphocyst (with abscess)	1 (0.68%)	0
Hematoma of anterior abdominal wall	2 (1.4%)	0
Pelvic abscess	1 (0.68%)	0
Intra-abdominal hemorrhage	1 (0.68%)	0
Vaginal stump dehiscence (vaginal necrosis)	1 (0.68%)	1 (1.5%)

Discussion. The analysis we conducted indicates the necessity of careful patient selection for minimally invasive surgery. Possible limitations of the study include the fact that the groups were not comparable in terms of tumor size during postoperative staging: in the laparoscopic surgery group, the majority of patients had tumors smaller than 2 cm, while in the open surgery group, most patients had tumors larger than 2 cm.

Table 3

Recurrences in the Open Surgery Group for Cervical Cancer (CC)

Recurrence Localization	Time of Recurrence	Medical History	Outcome
Iliac Lymph Nodes	12 months	T2a1NoM0, para-aortic lymphadenectomy	Alive
Local (Vagina)	6 years	T1b1NoMo, ovarian transposition	Alive
Inguinal Lymph Nodes	12 months	T1b1NoMo	Death
Bones	12 months	T1a2N0Mo	Alive
Local	3 years	TisNoMo	Alive
Lungs	12 months	T1b1N1Mo, endophytic tumor growth, adjuvant radiotherapy	Death
Local	4 years	T1b1NoMo, ovarian transposition	Alive
Iliac Lymph Nodes	2 years	Endophytic tumor growth, T1b2N0Mo	Alive
Local	3 years	T1b1NoMo	Alive
Supraclavicular Lymph Nodes	12 months	T1aNoMo, ovarian transposition	Death
Para-aortic Lymph Nodes, Supraclavicular Lymph Nodes, Liver	12 months	T2a1N1M0	Death
Local	12 months	T1b2N0Mo	Death
Lungs	12 months	T1b2NiMo, clear-cell histotype, lymphovascular invasion, adjuvant radiotherapy	Alive
Lungs, Kidney	3 years	T1b1NoMo, adenocarcinoma, poorly differentiated tumor, adjuvant radiotherapy	Alive
Local	3 years	TisNoMo, ovarian transposition	Alive
Ovary	5 months	T1b2NoMo, poorly differentiated lymphovascular i	

Another potential limitation is the longer follow-up period in the open surgery group (since 2010) because laparoscopic extended hysterectomy technology was introduced in our department only in 2019. All surgeries were performed by experienced surgeons, so we did not observe an influence of surgeon experience (learning curve) on the long-term results. The higher number of recurrences in the open surgery group can be explained by the fact that the study was not randomized, and patients with known poor prognostic factors, such as tumor size, histotype, disease stage, and age, were more likely to undergo open surgery.

Thus, our results are comparable with data from other studies and recommendations from NCCN and ESGO. For patients with tumors smaller than 2 cm, we also confirm the safety and advantages of laparoscopy, particularly in terms of faster rehabilitation. We would like to emphasize again the importance of carefully selecting patients for laparoscopic surgery.

Table 4

Characteristic	Open Surgery (n = 147)	Laparoscopic Surgery (n = 65)
One-year mortality	1.4%	0%
Overall survival	95.9%	96.9%

Conclusion. The recurrence rate after laparoscopic extended hysterectomy (1.5%) does not exceed the recurrence rate after open extended hysterectomy (12.9%), which demonstrates the effectiveness of both laparoscopic and open extended hysterectomy.

Overall survival (95.9% and 96.9%, respectively) and one-year mortality (1.4% and 0%, respectively) did not significantly differ between the two groups, further supporting the effectiveness of both laparoscopic and open extended hysterectomy.

The number of intraoperative and postoperative complications after laparoscopic extended hysterectomy did not exceed the number of complications seen after open extended hysterectomy, indicating the safety of the laparoscopic approach.

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For citation: Mamedov U.S., Nurov J.R., Abdurahimova Y.A. The role of laparoscopic surgery in the recurrence of cervical cancer // *Bulletin of Fundamental and Clinic Medicine*. – 2025. – № 6(20). – P. 148–153. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17570525>